

A facile and sensitive spectrophotometric analysis of sulfonamides in pure form and its pharmaceuticals

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A sensitive and simple spectrophotometric method for the determination of sulfonamides in either pure form or its pharmaceutical formulations is described. The method is based on the formation of red coloured product by the reaction of the sulfonamides with promethazine hydrochloride (PH) in presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) in acidic medium. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 0.1–15 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ at λ_{max} 510 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivities are 10420.0–12630.0 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and 0.019–0.0236 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Many spectrophotometric methods have been reported for the determination of sulfa drugs¹. But all these methods in one way or the other suffer from several disadvantages. To overcome the shortcomings of the existing procedures authors have made some attempts and succeeded in developing a sensitive and accurate spectrophotometric method for the determination of sulfonamides in bulk samples and its pharmaceutical formulations using promethazine hydrochloride (PH).

It is interesting to note that PH, an important derivative of phenothiazines, chemically known as 10-(2-dimethylaminopropyl)-phenothiazine, itself belongs to another class of drugs (antihistamine), has been effectively employed as a reagent in the present method.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra of the coloured product :

NBS oxidizes PH to phenothiazinyl free radical, which on coupling with sulfonamide gave unstable light green coloured product. However, when it was extracted with dichloromethane, it gave a stable and intense red colour with λ_{max} at 510 nm. The factors affecting the colour development, reproducibility, sensitivity and validity to Beer's law were investigated with sulfacetamide (SA) as the model compound. The other sulfonamides behaved similarly. The colourless reagent blank had practically negligible absorbance at this wavelength.

In order to establish the optimum conditions necessary for a rapid and quantitative formation of the coloured product with maximum stability, the absorbance of a series of solutions was measured by varying one and fixing other parameters at 510 nm. It was found that 1 g dm^{-3} solution of PH in the range 1.0–2.0 ml and 0.1 g dm^{-3} solution of

NBS in the range 3.5–4.5 ml were necessary to achieve the maximum colour intensity of the product with maximum stability. Therefore, 1.5 ml of PH and 4 ml of NBS solutions were recommended for all measurements.

Carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, benzene, dichloromethane were tested as extractive solvents for the proposed reaction. Dichloromethane was preferred to other for its selective extraction. It offers advantages such as being economically cheaper and convenient to be used as extractive solvent.

Reaction mechanism :

Based on the Job's method of continuous variation, it was found that sulfonamide interacted with the cited reagent in the ratio of 1 : 1. This obviously supports the assumptions that a methylene blue-like structure is formed. On the basis of the available literature² the probable mechanism is presented in Scheme 1. PH [I] interacts with NBS to form

Scheme 1

Table 1. Parameters for the spectrophotometric determination of sulfonamide derivatives

Parameter	SD	SA	SMx	SG	SMt	ST	SMr
Beer's law range ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.25–15	0.1–15	0.1–15	0.1–15	0.1–15	0.25–15	0.25–15
Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	11000.0	10870.0	12444.0	10420.0	11790.0	12630.0	12200.0
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.0210	0.0190	0.0217	0.0205	0.0236	0.0202	0.0216
Photometric range ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.8–13	0.5–13	0.5–13	0.5–13	0.5–13	0.8–13	0.8–13
Correlation constant							
Slope ^a	0.0441	0.0514	0.043	0.049	0.0376	0.0489	0.0458
Intercept	0.0121	0.003	0.0161	0.003	0.026	0.0043	0.0047
Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)	0.9980	0.9990	0.9997	0.9990	0.9993	0.9987	0.9984
RSD (%) ^b	1.20	1.14	1.08	1.10	1.22	1.18	1.22
<i>t</i> values (<i>n</i> = 5, at 95% confidence level tabulated value 2.57)	0.97	1.04	1.28	0.78	0.91	0.68	1.11
<i>F</i> values (<i>n</i> ₁ and <i>n</i> ₂ ^c = 5, at 95% confidence level tabulated value is 5.05)	2.72	2.32	2.00	1.86	1.64	1.91	2.65

^a $Y = ax + b$ where *x* is the concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of sulfonamides. ^bCalculated from five determinations. ^cResults are correlated with respect to official pharmacopoeial method.

SD = sulfadiazine, SA = sulfacetamide, SMx = sulfamethoxazole, SG = sulfaguanidine, SMt = sulfamethazole, ST = sulfathiazole and SMr = sulfamerazine.

the phenothiazinyl free radical [II]. Following this, II oxidizes to the PH cation, which has the resonating forms III, IV and V. Thus, the lowest electron density on the PH cation found at positions C-3, C-7 and S-5, which permits a nucleophilic attack at positions 3 or 7 by sulfonamide to form methylene blue-like dyestuff VI or VII.

The parameters for the determination of sulfonamides are presented in Table I.

The reaction between PH and NBS and successive coupling by sulfonamide was found to be instantaneous. The coloured products were found stable up to 35°. At higher temperature the drug concentration was found to increase due to volatile nature of dichloromethane. As a result the absorbance values of the coloured product increased. However, the resultant product was stable for more than 20 h at 25 ± 3°.

Interference studies :

The effect of the concomitants associated with the sulfonamides in its pure form and its formulations were investigated by taking SA as model compound. This method does not suffer any interference from commonly associated excipients and additives used in the preparation of table or eye drops such as sucrose, lactose, dextrose, starch, talc, magnesium alginate, sodium alginate and stearic acid. However, ascorbic acid, being a reducing agent, found to oxidize simultaneously alongwith PH and therefore interfere in the proposed reaction.

Experimental

A Jasco UVIDEc-160 UV-VIS spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm matched cells was used.

Sulfonamides and PH (both Sigma) were used. All other chemicals used were A.R. grade. Deionized water was used to prepare all solutions. Freshly prepared solutions were always employed. Standard solution ($1000 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of each sulfonamide (100 mg) were prepared in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} HCl (2–3 ml) and then diluted to 100 ml with deionized water. A working standard solution of each sulfonamide containing $25 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ was prepared by further dilution. A 1 g dm^{-3} solution of PH and 0.1 g dm^{-3} solution of NBS were prepared in water.

Procedure :

Solutions of 1.5 ml PH and 4 ml NBS were added to various amounts (0.05–20 μg) of each sulfonamide solutions (working standard) in a series of separating flasks, followed by the addition of dichloromethane (3 ml). The contents were shaken well for 1 min and set aside for 1–2 min. The separated organic phase was separated and the aqueous phase was again extracted with the same solvent ($3 \times 3 \text{ ml}$). The extracts were mixed, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and made upto 10 ml with the same solvent. Its absorbance was measured at 510 nm against a blank.

Separation of sulfonamide in a formulation combined with trimethoprim :

Weighed out 20 tablets accurately and grinded them to

a fine powder. A portion of the powder is weighed out accurately and triturated it with a minimum amount of 1 M sodium hydroxide at 60° to dissolve the sulfonamide. After cooling, the mixture was transferred into a 50 ml standard flask and diluted upto the mark with deionized water, left for 2 h to let the undissolved trimethoprim settle³. After filtration, the filtrate was analysed for sulfonamide as described above.

The applicability of the method for the assay of available pharmaceutical formulations was examined. Results obtained by the proposed method agree well with the official pharmacopoeial method. Lower values of standard deviation for five determinations indicate good precision of the method. To check the potential interference from the commonly used additives, recovery analysis was also carried out. For this, to a known amount of drug, varying amount of additive was added and analyzed. Recovery is found to be around 100% with lower value of RSD ($n = 5$). These results clearly indicate the utility of the proposed method for the analysis of sulfa drugs in pure form and dosage forms. Hence, this approach may be considered for the determination of sulfa drugs in quality control laboratories.

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